

Systematic Theology Paper for Apologetic Science Phd Candidates Submitted to the Management of East African Polytechnic College Kyambogo for the Award of a Doctoral Professional Dipolma Level Eight in Apologetic Science

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DOCTORATE OF THEOLOGY IN APOLOGETIC SCIENCE
THEOLOGY IN APOLOGETIC SCIENCE SYSTEMATIC THEOLOGY BOOK

LETTER OF AUTHORISATION

I **NALOKA BAKER FREDERICK** do here by attest that the Systematic Theology Book is truthful, current and accurate to my best of knowledge.

Sign.....

Date:..30-10-2022.....

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Am indebted to my group members as well as our research supervisor Professor Kibalama Johnson and his assistant; Dr. Kitaka who introduced to me this program and encouraged me to take it on with all the responsibilities that I hold. I never knew I could handle it, however the encouragement and time invested to show me that it is possible was and is all worth it.

LETTER OF TRASMITAL

I submit in my Systematic Theology Book containing a body of knowledge researched from different sources of literature. I have carried out this study objectively with due care and diligence so as to come up with a standard module PhD candidate studying systematic theology. I have acknowledged

Sources of information by quotations proper referencing. Therefore, I tried as much as possible to complete this study truthfully and correctly.

In case you need any assistance in interpreting this study, please contact me. I will be happy if you I will be grateful if you read this book your corrective action.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'A. Balurka', written over a horizontal line.

Signature.....

Date...30-10-2022.....

DEDICATION

This book is dedicated to the following people for the support they rendered during my research work. My work colleagues, that have been a vital factor to my coming up with this work research and I would not have achieved this without their support. Furthermore, I dedicated my work to my supervisor Professor Kibalama and Dr. Kitaka for their valuation research inputs.

Unto my parents, who saw the best in me, one who turned many door-handles to get me into a place that could support and sponsor my education.

Unto my wonderful wife and children that have at times missed out on being with me, and have had to put up with me when I was stressing with deadlines.

DECLARATION

I NALOKA BAKER FREDERICK declare that the Systematic Theology Paper is my own original composition and it has never been submitted to any institution of higher learning

APPROVAL

This is to certify NALOKA BAKER FREDERICK completed this work about production of Systematic Theology Book and we have peer reviewed it, it is ready to be submitted with approval of;

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ABSTRACT

Systematic describes the parameters of the discussion. It is not simply on attempts to an all-encompassing method, but more importantly a structured development of the conversation about God.

Since systematic theology studies God in relationship to and alongside of the truth revealed in the arts and sciences, it is often considered the pinnacle of theological scholarship.

The church has been entrusted with God’s revelation and to steward the word of truth, we must confess the bible’s teaching with clarity and conviction. A systematic Christian theology is both a biblical faithful and historically informative, providing a fresh synthesis of the essential doctrines of the faith. It brings fresh insight that many nonsystematic theologies lack.

With readable prose, suggestions for further study and discussion questions, Christian theology will equip students and pastors to clarify and articulate what they believe and why.

I have written this paper for students and also for every Christian who has a hunger to know the central doctrines of the Bible in greater depth.

This researched paper is in tandem with the met-analysis curriculum developed for PhD candidates offering apologetic science.

ACADEMIC PEER REVIEW

I have reviewed this researched book and found it a material for a PhD academic course unit. It equips students and Bible readers to think more coherently, and be able to intelligently give an answer about the hope we have in Christ. It enables us to tackle any controversial topics exegetically, that have otherwise fragmented the body of Christ.

Sign..... Date...20-03-2023...

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Systematic theology is defined differently by different scholars as a type of theology that distills an orderly, rational and coherent accounts of doctrines of Christian faith. One of experts of systematic theology is John Frame, who defines it as a study that explains what the Bible teaches about any given topic. E.g., where does a person go after death?

Another expert, is Professor Wayne Gruden, who defines it as a theology that collects and comprehending all the relevant passages in the Bible on various topics and then summarizes their teachings clearly so as to know what to believe about each topic.

It should be noted, at this juncture, that systematic theology involves compiling and comprehending all pertinent passages in the Bible and then encapsulate them in clear, teachable form so that we have a firm foundation for our beliefs. Systematic theology, therefore interacts directly with the scripture and not with extra-biblical sources like dreams, visions, audible or still voices, divine encounters, etc.

It also incorporates on biblical disciplines like church history, Bible history and history of theology.

Systematic theology also shares its systematic tasks with other disciplines such as constructive theology, dogmatics, ethics, apologetics and philosophy of religion.

Systematic theology refers to something being put into a system of divisions that explain its various arrears. For example, many books of the Bible give information about the angels. No single book gives all information about angels. Systematic theology takes all the information about angels from all the books of the Bible and then organizes it into a system called Angelology. In a similar vein, various books of the Bible talk about curses. And how it can be avoided; Resurrection of the Dead; falling into a trance under the power of God; Wolves in sheep's' clothing, etc.

Systematic theology groups all into one topic for each category of doctrine into a schematized expository topic, e.g. "Deliverance of Generation Curses", "Life After Death", "Drunk in the Spirit", etc. In my publications, I have grouped various teachings mentioned in the Bible like faith, prosperity, sickness, giving; into one expository categorical Topic "Word of Faith Theology". This enables scholars to deepen their research in sound doctrine. So, that is what systematic theology is all about by organizing the teachings of the Bible into categorical systems.

Systematic theology is so unique that it centers on studying the entire scope of the Bible on what every scripture teaches about a particular topic or issue.

Lexham Bible Dictionary summarizes this type of theology as follows:

"An approach to Bible that seeks to draw Biblical teachings and themes into a self-consistent, coherent whole in conversation with the historical teachings and themes into self-consistent, coherent whole, in conversation with the history of Christian theological reflections and contemporary issues confronting the church. This distinction, though related to the approach of Biblical theology, which focuses on the development of theological themes within individual books of the Bible. The practice of biblical theology is often more closely intertwined with the practice of biblical studies, whereas systematic theology is usually viewed as a displace that goes beyond the scope of biblical studies into church history, philosophy, and pastoral application.

Systematic theology involves collecting, scientifically arranging, comparing, exhibiting, and defending facts from every source concerning God and his works, in a carefully organized manner and then making a claim on that data.

To explain further, you could study the book of Daniel teaching on the end times in context of the entire Bible-this is biblical theology. Furthermore, studying how people in different time period understood end times, which is historical theology. However, when it comes to Bible's teaching on end times to every life falls under practical theology.

Andrew Nasell, assistant professor of New Testament and biblical theology at Bethlehem College and Seminary, suggests at least 10 doctrines with big headings under which systematic theology is classified below:

- Theology Proper or Patrology
- Christology is the study,
- Christian Anthropology,
- Pneumatology,
- Soteriology,
- Angelology,
- Hermeneutics,
- Christian Demonology,
- Eschatology,
- Soteriology is the study of salvation,
- Ecclesiology

Details are below:

A. The lesson teaching the character of God is Theology proper or Patrology

This one focuses on God's attributes or his character. It spells out his existence, his immortality, his divine authority, his love and mercy, his wrath and judgement, etc.

It explains the distinction between Godhead but at the same time maintains the unity of the Godhead.

This study explains that God as a sovereign being, self-satisfied, self-existent, self-directed. On the other hand, it teaches that man does not determine his destiny and without Jesus' man cannot do anything.

This theology teaches that God is omnipresent, omnipotent, omniscient and eternal.

Patrology teaches that God is not only a loving father full of love and compassion and mercy, but that God is consuming fire who will unleash his wrath on the wicked. God does both the punishment of sin but he forgives repentant sinners (Romans 11:33).

B. The study of the Son of God is Christology.

Christology terminology comes from a Greek word called Messiah/Christ combined to form the study of the person and work of Jesus Christ.

Christology answers questions concerning the nature of Christ, what he came to do on earth and his divine mission on earth.

This study explains that Jesus was one of the Godhead and that he was both God and man. It teaches Jesus left his glory in heaven but he never left his divinity.

It teaches his virgin birth, his death on the cross, his resurrection from the dead and his eventual ascension to heaven. Most importantly his virgin birth and he being the first fruit in the resurrection. Meaning he is the only dead person who has ever come out of the grave. All who have died are still waiting for his return to be resurrected from the dead.

C. The teaching about the Holy Spirit is called Pneumatology

The Greek word which means Wind or Air is known as Pneumatology. The combination of words air, wind and spirit is coined to mean Pneumatology to refer to the study of the Holy Spirit.

The indwelling of the Holy Spirit to a person occurs immediately at the time of getting saved. The indwelling of the Holy Spirit is for all believers.

Many Christians have an unbiblical perception of the Holy Spirit. Some understand the Holy Spirit as a power or force given to us from God. This is not biblical. Pneumatology teaches us that the Holy Spirit is a Person, with a mind, emotions, and will. The Holy Spirit is Jesus' "replacement" on earth (John 14:16-26; 15:26; 16:7). The Holy Spirit is received at salvation (Romans 8:9) and is the permanent possession of every believer in Christ (Ephesians 1:13-14). Pneumatology helps us to understand these issues and recognize the Biblical roles of the Holy Spirit in our lives today.

The study of Pneumatology is of immense benefit to the Christian. In the pages of Scripture, we come face to face with the third Person of the Trinity, God Himself in spirit, and we see His very personal and intimate ministry to us. Through Him, we come to know God's love for us "because the love of God has been poured out in our hearts by the Holy Spirit who was given to us" (Romans 5:5). To understand the ministry of the Holy Spirit is to find joy in His role as our Comforter (John 16:7; Acts 9:31) who not only helps and comforts us, but who comes to our rescue when our hearts are so burdened, we cannot even pray for relief (Romans 8:26). When we pursue the knowledge of the Holy Spirit we find, to our great delight, that He not only lives within us, but He does so forever, never to leave or forsake us (John 14:16). All these truths are burned into our hearts when we study Pneumatology.

A good summary verse for Pneumatology is John 16:8-11, "When He (the Holy Spirit) comes, He will convict the world of guilt in regard to sin and righteousness and judgment: in regard to sin, because men do not believe in me; in regard to righteousness, because I am going to the Father, where you can see me no longer; and in regard to judgment, because the prince of this world now stands condemned."

D. Soteriology deals with salvation of mankind.

The study concerning the doctrine of salvation is called soteriology. It teaches that Christ's death secures the salvation of those who repent. It explains the teaching of redemption, justification, sanctification and atonement of Jesus on the Cross.

It teaches that we attain this salvation by grace alone, through faith alone, and by Christ alone and according to scriptures alone to the glory of God alone.

Because we come to know that He who can never fail is the means by which we were saved and the means by which we remain secure in our salvation. If we were responsible to save ourselves and keep ourselves saved, we would fail. Thank God that is not the case!

Titus 3:5-8 is a tremendous summary of Soteriology, "He saved us, not because of righteous things we had done, but because of His mercy. He saved us through the washing of rebirth and renewal by the Holy Spirit, whom He poured out on us generously through Jesus Christ our Savior, so that, having been justified by His grace, we might become heirs having the hope of eternal life."

E. Ecclesiology is the study of the church leadership.

Ecclesiology is the study of the church. The word Ecclesiology comes from two Greek words meaning "assembly" and "word" - combining to mean "the study of the church." The church is the assembly of believers who belong to God. Ecclesiology is crucial to understand God's purpose for believers in the world today. Some important issues in Ecclesiology are:

What is the church? Many people today understand the church to be a building. This is not the biblical understanding of the church. The root meaning of "church" is not that of a building, but of people.

What is the purpose of the church? According to Scripture, the purposes / activities of the church should be: (1) teaching Biblical doctrine, (2) providing a place of fellowship for believers, (3) observing the Lord's supper, and (4) praying.

What is the importance of Christian baptism? According to the Bible, Christian baptism is simply a step of obedience, a public proclamation of one's faith in Christ alone for salvation. While baptism is not required for salvation, it is an act of obedience and faith—evidence that salvation is a reality in a person's life.

What is the importance of the Lord's Supper / Christian Communion? A study of the Lord's Supper is a soul-stirring experience because of the depth of meaning that it portrays. It is an "acted out sermon," remembering our Lord's death and resurrection, and looking to the future for His return in glory.

What does the Bible say about the form of church government? The Bible teaches that church leadership consists of a plurality of elders along with a group of deacons who serve as servants of the church. But it is not contrary to this plurality of elders to have one of these elders serving in the major "pastoral" role.

Ecclesiology helps us to understand the role of the church and our role in the church. It teaches us about the ordinances of the church, how church leadership is to be chosen and structured, and what the church is to be doing in regards to believers (worship and discipleship) and unbelievers (ministry and evangelism). A Biblical understanding of Ecclesiology would go a long way to correct many of the common problems in churches today. Above all, we must understand that the church is the Body of Christ and that each of us has a specific function and role within that body.

A key Scripture on Ecclesiology is Acts 2:42, "They devoted themselves to the apostles' teaching and to the fellowship, to the breaking of bread and to prayer."

F. The end time study is Eschatology

Eschatology is the study of what the Bible says is going to happen in the end times. Many treat Eschatology as an area of theology to be avoided. Of course, Eschatology is not as crucial as Christology or Soteriology. That does not mean, though, that it is unimportant to a Biblical worldview. How we understand Eschatology has an impact on how we should live our lives and what we are to expect to occur in God's plan. Some important issues in Eschatology are these:

The study concerning the doctrine of salvation is called soteriology. It teaches that Christ's death secures the salvation of those who repent. It explains the teaching of redemption, justification, sanctification and atonement of Jesus on the Cross.

It teaches that we attain this salvation by grace alone, through faith alone, and by Christ alone and according to scriptures alone to the glory of God alone.

G. The End Times

Although the word Rapture does not appear in scriptures, it's taught especially in the New Testament. It means the second coming of Christ to take believers beginning with the dead in Christ who will come to life and come out first, then those who will be alive will be transformed in a twinkling of an eye and join Christ in the air for a thousand years.

After the a thousand years, Christ will return on earth to physically save the remnant of Israel, then final judgment will occur.

There exists some controversy in end time teachings because of different subjective interpretations of the bible. But by and large, this does not absolve us from the ones to read, study and understand end time event. After all the book of Revelation begins by promising a blessing to those who read, hears and those who put into practice what is written in that prophetic book.

A good knowledge and understanding of end times prophetic messages will take away fears we may harbor about the future perilous times because of the security God promised believers.

H. Christian Anthropology is the study of humanity and his nature

It focuses in detail; the nature of man and how material and immaterial aspects of man relate to each other by answering what it means to be made in the image of God which enables him to communicate with God. What is meant to be the likeness of God is the social, mental and the moral aspects.

This study wrestles with issues concerning the nature of man and his relationship with his maker. It tackles whether man was created with the Holy Spirit or not. It answers questions like how many parts did God create man with? his origin and his destiny.

Anthropology enables us to understand ourselves from the perspective of God. It clearly teaches us concerning our total depravity ie our fallen nature which keeps us from determining our destiny. That's why God saw our helplessness and sent Jesus on the cross to redeem us out of it.

I. The study concerning sin is called Hematology

The study about sin is known as hematology. It explains the origin and consequences of sin (Romans 3:23)

It explains the definition of sin as the breaking of God's law (1John 4:4) and how man rebels against the Almighty. (Joshua 1:18)

Hematology teaches that sins are the same and have punishment in hell. (Romans 6:23)

It explains that before we need a savior, we must understand why.

The fact out of this study we understand that we are sinners by inheritance that we are sinners by inheritance, by birth or by choices we make in life.

Until we understand the depth and the danger of our sinful nature, we may not need the savior as a ransom.

We are all sinners by inheritance and fall short of the glory of God but we are justified by grace, by the redemption of Jesus Christ on the cross. (Romans 3:23-29)

J. The about Angels

The study of angels teaches us about angels and they relate to human beings and how they execute God's purpose on earth.

Angels have no gender and are mortal heavenly beings. They were created being in a higher order of creation than that of human beings.

Angels do a lot of functions on earth like protecting believers and punishing offenders.

Angels do a lot in heaven before God's throne like worshipping etc.

Angels help us and interfere in our warfare against Satan. Since we know that angels are created beings like us, we need not to worship them or glorify them because it robs God his glory because it was God who sent Jesus to redeem us and not angels.

K. Hermeneutics is the study of proper interpretation of the Bible

The study of principles that help interpret the bible very well is called hermeneutics.

It's in tandem with Paul's admonition to Timothy that in order to be approached by God he should correctly or rightfully handle the word of truth. What Paul meant was that he should interpret, understand and apply the bible in a proper way which God approves.

The most important principle of interpretation is that we should interpret it literally.

The second is that the bible does not contradict itself. So if interpretations contradict other verses, then the problem is the bible reader not God's intention.

Another important principle is that the reader should interpret according to the meaning of the context. Another is the scriptures are the best interpreters of themselves i.e if there is a difficult verse, you should use another scripture to interpret it. This will protect us from misinterpretation of scriptures and impose the meaning from the reader other than from the intended other's meaning. I have published a book on this topic. Other ways theology can be divided bellow:

➤ *Demonology is the study about Demons*

The study about demons is known as demonology and it's related to the study of angels. It explains what they are and its origin and how they attack us. It goes ahead to teach us how to fight demonic warfare by putting on all armors of God. Demons are fallen angels which fell on earth together with Satan after a failed attempt to overthrow God from his heavenly throne.

At the moment, their aim is to fight human beings who believe in God through Jesus Christ. The bible teaches that demons can oppress people but cannot completely possess believers.

Satan and his demons sometimes pretend to be angels of light in their deceitful schemes against mankind.

Systematic theology helps us to understand scriptures by its deeper dive into the details of each topic. For example, through systematic theology we get to know how to pray when we are confronted by Satan and his demons. We are not to directly rebuke, bind Satan with chains or ropes and throw him to dry lands. Rather we solicit the Lord Jesus to rebuke him on our behalf. After all, Jesus said that we can do nothing on our own without his help. This calls for us to be calm, watchful and stay close to our Lord Jesus for protection.

➤ *Biblical theology:*

Biblical theology focuses on the teachings of the individual authors and books of the Bible and places each teaching in the Scriptures' historical development. It is a presentation of the Old and New Testament writers' theological teachings within their historical setting.

A Biblical theologian may ask, "What is the historical development of the teaching about the kingdom of God as it is seen throughout the history of the Old Testament and then of the New Testament?" The Biblical theologian analyzes the development of each doctrine through the historical development of scripture. They organize the topics historically and in the order that the bible presents the topics. Biblical theology's main task is expounding the theology found in the Bible in its own historical setting and its own terms, categories, and

thought-forms. The Biblical theologian seeks to learn what the biblical authors believed and taught in the context of their own historical setting. It is primarily a descriptive type of theology. It is not initially concerned with the final meaning of the Bible's teachings or their relevance for today. This meaning and relevance is the task of systematic theology. It is the study of a certain book (or books) of the Bible and emphasizing the different aspects of theology it focuses on. For example, the Gospel of John is very Christological since it focuses so much on the deity of Christ (John 1:1, 14; 8:58; 10:30; 20:28). While the book of Revelation mainly talks about future events that will happen when Christ returns at the end of the age.

➤ *The History of Theology*

The study of Christian doctrines and how they have developed over the centuries is known as the history of theology. I have addressed this issue ably in other papers. This study examines the development and the historical roots of Orthodox Church. This study also examines how different Christian denominations have developed their doctrines through subject interpretations of the bible.

This study covers various denominational creeds and their statements of faith, church councils, and doctrinal heresies that have and been dealt with throughout church history. A good student of historical theology studies the development of Orthodox doctrines so as to identify true doctrine from false doctrine and cultic movement.

Historic theology goes deep into their periods of church history so that the Christian, through significant exegesis can respond to false teachings. Its unwise for a person to present their views without engaging historical theology at all.

There is a close link between historical theology and church history because church history for example leads to understanding how different doctrines have led to divisions heresy within the church.

Historical theology helps us to understand how different denominations and different interpretations of the Bible have come up. This will help the church leaders to go back to the historical church and faith which was given to the saints.

➤ *Dogmatic theology*

This type one teaches the actual orthodox doctrine, its name is derived from a Greek word called dogma or an authoritative and sanctioned belief systems.

Although the term dogmatic theology first appeared in 1659, it was more perceive during the reformation when it was useful in designing the church creeds or articles of faith of the reformers. Dogmatic theology was useful in the early church councils in fighting heretical teachings that rocked the church then. Systematic theology and dogmatic theology sometimes are synonymous. However the difference of those two is that while systematic theology directly requires a denomination all body connection and sanction.

However, both use the same outline and structure in their theological conversations.

➤ *Contemporary Movements of theology.*

Good examples theological movements that have come in focus since World War 1 are:

Word of Faith Theology (WOF), New Apostolic Reformation Theology (NAR), Positive Mental Attitude (PMA), Generation Curses Theology, Strategic Spiritual Level Warfare (SSLWF), Church Growth Movement, Seeker-Sensitive Movement, The Joel Army, The Elijah Company, and all new forms of Revivalists Charismatic Movements yet to come. Contemporary theology studies theological covenant trends of theology from World War 1 to the covenant period. Here this theology spans from the 20th century to date. The major denominations focused in the study include charismatics, evangelicals, Pentecostals, neo-Pentecostals, new apostolic reformations. The later rain, post Vatican 11 Catholicism, Word of Faith

Movements, Feminism, Liberal Theology Movements. We may not develop into experts of all contemporary theology but its worth the effort if one carries a good apologetic ministry.

Contemporary theology, being a fertile field of scholars, it confronts intellectual challenges facing theology, science and social issues and religious challenges.

Contemporary study enables scholars to detect any deviations from historical theology, hence corrective measures can be done to restore doctoral purity in the church (Jude 3).

No matter what method of theology is studied, what is important is that theology is studied to the benefit of the body of Christ. I have also addressed this arrear about the dangers of contemporary theology exhaustively as well in my other papers.

Systematic theology also covers other fields such as apologetics, logic, and exegesis and coherently organize what scripture says about these particular topics. Bible doctrine is like butter on bread when it comes to systematic theology. In other words, bible theology is the doctrines of the bible arranged in accordance to their chronology and historical background. While systematic theology categorizes doctrines according to topics as stated earlier. Systematic theology can spice up how you exegete a particular text. However, in case your systematic theology framework is not correct, then that can disorganize how you exegete a particular text.

➤ *Practical Theology*

The study that makes it useful to apply theology is called practical theology, so as to be relevant and useful in our daily lives. It helps students to apply the knowledge into effective ministry focused persons. This will culminate in transforming ministries into effective communicators of scriptures so as to bring growth of believers while they remain servants.

The main gist of practical theology is to equip Christian leaders with knowledge and professional skills to minister effectively in this modern world.

CHAPTER TWO

HISTORY OF SYSTEMATIC THEOLOGY

Much as systematic theology existed in early days of the church, it was not known pervasively as it is today. It was titled as such by a German theologian by the name Bartholomaeus Beckerman (1572-1609)

It should be noted that Bereans did practices systematic theology by combining scriptures in effort to ascertain the truth. (Acts 17:10-12)

Likewise, all the Old Testament seers and early church fathers were systematic research practitioners because they diligently discovered how and when Christ will come to save mankind.

One medieval systematic theologian by the name John of Damascus (675-749AD) sought to develop instructions for the church. During the 17th century the Westminster confession developed into an advanced form of systematic theology. Many Presbyterian churches are still adopting this confession as an article of faith.

During the enlightenment period of between late 17th century and early 18th centrally, there was apostasy partly due to departure from systematic theology instincts until 1872-1872 when Charles Hodge produced a systematic theology book which is the most referenced text book.

Christ's redemption. (Peter 1:10:11).

Protestant groups developed a new form of systematic theology around the 19th century by proving that doctrine formed a more coherent system on one or more fundamental axiom.

The most recent generations of evangelicals are regarded as the most intellectual Christians who are highly regarded systematic theologians.

New authors are producing numerous books on the subject of systematic theology.

CHAPTER THREE

THE DISPARITY OF SYSTEMATIC THEOLOGY AND BIBLICAL THEOLOGY

On one hand systematic theology uses the entire Bible to discover doctrines about Biblical topics, e.g. about God, man, Christ, the Holy spirit, the church, wolves in sheep's clothing, Hermeneutics, and each subsets. Biblical theology is part of systematic theology, the difference between biblical theology and systematic theology is that biblical theology organizes topics as they are found in the bible. Biblical theology does not cover topics which span the entire bible like systematic theology does.

The following are complete list of theology.

- Historical theology
- Apologetics
- Philosophical

I have given a detailed exposition about apologetics as my concentration paper

CHAPTER FOUR

THE IMPORTANCE OF SYSTEMATIC THEOLOGY

Systematics is theology is a daily rationalization because we depend on how the bible spells out to us in order to comprehend the doctrine of man in terms of his creation, gender, his sin natives and how to relate with Almighty God.

Its imperative to peruse through the whole pages of scriptures. The best tools to help us in the search are concordances, dictionaries, topical indexes etc. in Uganda a good example is the Luganda Bible which has good indexes for research purposes.

The whole idea about systematic theology is its systematics organized truth in a logical manner. Normally Christian theological scholars who are skillful, accurate, do apply systematic theology. Needless to say we need to be aware that its strong points are related to its weak points so that we don't go off truck.

Some of the good causes requiring us to study systematic theology are:

A. It encourages us to rejoice in our savior

When we pray and petition our Lord and study the word, God illuminates our eyes and hearts to his revelations, as the Holy spirit illuminates us, we begin to sing hymns in our hearts.

B. It guides our lessons as we tutor others

It brings a of bible knowledge which makes sense in what we teach to others. This may be on individual or to multitudes the proper understanding of scripture will enhance our teachings.

C. It helps us to know where we go after death

As much as the Bible does not teach exhaustively about heaven, it definitely teaches that Jesus will come again to resurrect those dead from their graves for eternal destiny (John 14:13)

D. To know the reference what the Bible says about Christ Jesus

Systematic theology shows that Jesus is the center of our theology in scripture. These references were centered on Jesus even in the Old Testament through Christophany. (nonphysical).

E. Systematics in theology helps us to know our history

Right from Genesis up to the book of revelations we under where history begin and how it will end in glory.

F. It enables us to know why we believe

This knowledge will be enormous incorporating an apologetic ministry and evangelical ministry. This will safely guard us from wavering when we face worldly challenges which Jesus promised.

G. Systematic theology energizes us to obey the Lord's commission (matt28:19-20)

The truth is that the whole Bible is required to be used in assessing a topic. We see how Jesus quoted the Old Testament and how he established his authority in the New Testament. By knowing his commands, we are in obedience to God's will.

H. It will foster us to know God and love him more

Refereeing to his own teachings about himself in (2peter1:21), our love for him will increase when we read his word more and more.

As and whenever we study the bible systematically, we should petition God for his interventions. No one possesses complete knowledge. This implies that we get edification from fellow believers. We need to look for other people who are more mature and knowledgeable for counsel. But above all, seek wisdom form God. (Proverbs 2:6, 3:5-6:10, James 1:5-6)

CHAPTER FIVE

HOW WE SHOULD STUDY SYSTEMATIC THEOLOGY

Systematic theology draws on the main sacred text of Christianity using a methodical tradition different from biblical theology. At the same time it investigates the development of Christian doctrines over a period of time through philosophy, ethics, social science and natural science. Since systematic theology focusses on biblical truth, it is developed to directly interact with the contemporary world.

There are set guidelines in the Bible how to study systematic theology.

A. Systematic Theology should be studied prayerfully

The way we study systematic theology matters because it has to be aligned with prayer as Psalms 119;18 says: “Open my eyes that I may behold wondrous things out of your law”. Relentless request for more insight in understanding scriptures.

B. Humility is a requisite in systematic theology studies

Apostle Peter tells us “Clothes yourselves with humility towards one another for God opposes the proud but gives grace to the humble. (1peter 5:5). The element of pride comes in due to the fact systematic theology students learn and understand a lot of information which other Christians are not aware of. So keeping humble even arming with vital information which others don’t have is paramount.

C. Reasoning or logic is needed in systematic theological studies

It’s a common place to find Jesus and his Apostles quoted verses of scripture and make a reasonable deduction from it. (Acts 17:2)

Its proper to use human knowledge and human reason to come up with a conclusion from scriptural texts. However, we should be aware that sometimes we can make mistakes in our conclusions because these deductions are equal with scripture in authority. On scripture is the standard of truth.

Students of systematic theology should seek the help of some resources available like ESV systematic theology study Bible. Students can also look for other books on the subject like that of Wayne Gruden’s systematic theology, 2nd Edition. Use of technology by students can also be embraced to ease the study.

After getting the required text, then you should filter the results by use of denomination’s statement of faith and their position papers. About each topic.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION

The developers of systematic theology may be subjective in their study by interpreting scriptures eisegetically and not exegetically. Eisegesis is the interpretation of texts by imposing your own ideas while disregarding the author's intention of meaning. While exegesis interpretation maintains the author's intended meaning.

Another drawback to systematic theology developers is, that if a denomination statement of faith or its position papers are faulty, then the theological system will contain errors.

The bottom line is that systematic theology must interact directly with the scriptures rather than relying on extra-biblical sources like dreams, visions, angelic visitations, and audible voices. Relying on scriptures as final authority alone was one of the core principles of the 16th century reformers. Relying on extra-biblical sources while developing systematic theological resources ends heretical resources.

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